

Biased editorial on vitamin C in JAMA by Brant and Angus (2019)

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Comment on:

Brant EB, Angus DC.

Is High-Dose Vitamin C Beneficial for Patients With Sepsis?

JAMA. 2019 Oct 1;322(13):1257-1258.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31573621>

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In their editorial on vitamin C in JAMA, Brant and Angus write: “*Although unproven, common folklore holds that orange juice and lemons speed recovery from both influenza and the common cold, apparently due to a boost to the immune system. Linus Pauling, winner of 2 Nobel prizes, claimed a beneficial role for vitamin C across a wide range of diseases...*” [1].

This misleads readers. Linus Pauling carried out a meta-analysis – one of the very first in medicine – in which he concluded that vitamin C is beneficial against the common cold [2]. From 4 placebo-controlled trials, Pauling calculated that it was highly unlikely that the benefits reported in the vitamin C groups were explained by chance alone with $P = 0.000022$ [2]. Further controlled trials have corroborated Pauling’s conclusions [3-7]. Brant and Angus do not give any references to this literature. It is misleading to claim that the effect of vitamin C on the common cold is “unproven folklore”. The wide spread belief in mainstream medicine that vitamin C is ineffective against colds is explained by biased reviews which have been cited in numerous textbooks as medical folklore [6-9].

They also write “*Linus Pauling, winner of 2 Nobel prizes, claimed a beneficial role for vitamin C across a wide range of diseases, including terminal cancer (Ref 3)*” [1].

This is also misleading. Reference 3 is not a paper on vitamin C and cancer, but Pauling’s paper on vitamin C and evolution [10]. Thereby Brant and Angus make it seem that Pauling did not have

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

any empirical basis for his opinions on vitamin C and cancer. In fact, Pauling published 2 clinical studies on vitamin C and cancer in PNAS [11-13] and a long review on the biological plausibility of vitamin C effect in Cancer Research [14], but these papers were hidden from the readers of the editorial.

Brant and Angus further write about the CITRIS-ALI trial on vitamin C and sepsis [15]: “*The authors also evaluated 43 secondary outcomes, including a variety of measures of inflammation and organ recovery*” [1].

This is misleading. The study protocol of the CITRIS-ALI trial had only 18 secondary outcomes, not 43 [16]. Brant and Angus count numerous time points for the 18 secondary outcomes as if they were independent observations. However, measuring the same outcome several times does not make those measurements independent.

Furthermore, in EBM we are interested in clinically relevant outcomes and not in surrogates. There are numerous examples that demonstrate that the effects on surrogate endpoints can diverge from the effects on clinically relevant outcomes [17–20]. Surrogates/biomarkers are used because they are cheaper and faster than clinically relevant outcomes. However, they are used on the basis of assumption that they reflect the effects on clinically relevant outcomes. Thus, when there are direct data on clinically relevant outcomes, the findings on surrogates/biomarkers is irrelevant in EBM. In the CITRIS-ALI trial [15], there were only 4 clinically relevant outcomes and the primary focus should be on them [21].

Finally, Brant and Angus were not critical on the statistical analysis of survival in the CITRIS-ALI trial [15], when they write “*28-day all-cause mortality rates ... statistically significant without adjusting for multiple comparisons ($P = 0.01$)*” [1].

Visually it is evident that the ratio of the survival curves, on which the $P = 0.01$ is based, is not constant over time [15]. This was confirmed statistically as the 2-period Cox regression model is significantly better than the uniform model ($P = 0.006$ for testing the superiority of the 2-period model) [21]. Furthermore, compared to the model with no vitamin C effect over the 28-day period, the 2-period model improves the Cox regression with $P = 0.002$. Thus, the $P = 0.01$ uncritically reiterated by Brant and Angus gives a misleading impression of the differences between the vitamin C and placebo curves in the CITRIS-ALI trial. The differences are even less likely to be explained by chance [21].

This is not the first case when JAMA has misled its readers about vitamin C.

In 1975, JAMA published an RCT on vitamin C for the common cold by Thomas Karlowski, Thomas Chalmers et al. [22], which has been widely cited as evidence that vitamin C is ineffective. However, the statistical analysis of that study was flawed [8,23].

In 1975, JAMA also published a review on vitamin C for the common cold by Michael Dykes and Paul Meier [24], which has also been highly influential. However, the review was biased and misled readers [7,8]. Linus Pauling wrote another review in which he presented the results of relevant trials and his own interpretations, and criticism of Dykes and Meier’s arguments. Pauling submitted his manuscript to JAMA, but his paper was rejected even after Pauling twice made revisions to meet the suggestions of the referees. The manuscript was finally published in a minor journal [25,26]. The rejection of Pauling’s review was an unfortunate decision by JAMA, as it prevented the readers from seeing the other side of an important scientific controversy.

In 1987, JAMA published an official statement by the American Medical Association “*One of the most widely misused vitamins is ascorbic acid. There is no reliable evidence that large doses of ascorbic acid prevent colds or shorten their duration*” [27]. That statement was based wholly on Thomas Chalmers’ review [28]. However, there were significant errors also in this review, most notably in the extraction of data and in the calculations [6,8].

Finally, obfuscation in the reporting of the CITRIS-ALI trial findings in JAMA [15] was described in detail [21,29].

Thus, the editorial by Brant and Angus [1] was not the first case when JAMA has been misleading its readers on vitamin C.

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